

THE IMPACT OF REMOTE WORK ON EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING IN THE SERVICE INDUSTRY: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

Varnima Sharma

Research Scholar, School of Commerce and Management, Career Point University, Kota

Sandeep Kumar

Research Supervisor cum Associate Professor, School of Commerce and Management,
Career Point University, Kota

ABSTRACT

Work from home has increased the level of stress in employees and has affected the work life balance of many employees in the Service Industry. HR practitioners too plays a very significant role in strategic Human resource Management. Stress has affected the employee's performance, Proficiency in work, Job Satisfaction, Morale, Teamwork. This study aims to address for employees doing work from home and stress level for the employees, their work life balance, organization environment from human resource perspective. Work from home has become a practice now in every organization. There is less attention in physical and mental health of the employees in remote work. Thus, results will help us to understand the stress level of the employees on productivity and different workplace strategies to create effective work from home environment by helping to efficiently implement remote work policies that help the business to achieve the goals.

Keywords: Human Resource, Service Industry, Teamwork, Morale, Proficiency

INTRODUCTION

Work from home is playing a very important role in life of many employees and it affects the productivity in the organization. Organizations must create measures that help the employees in work from home and measures of easily communicating in case of any issues in at the time of work. Stress is one of the major factor by which there will be many problems as employees will not be abet perform well hence affecting the performance and lack of coordination. Work from home firstly requires to learn new online work doing skills along with how to communicate. Work from home requires proper attention in order to prevent problems employees need to be trained enough at first. Then for communication, timely video meeting should be held that will again encourage employees in work from home. There is imbalance work between job productivity and Human resource management. So the study supports various measures from human resource perspective.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Authors	Journal/Article	Conclusion
Systla Patanjali andNMK Bhattra 2022	<i>Work from Home During the Pandemic: The Impact of Organizational Factors on the Productivity of Employees in the IT Industry</i> The Journal of Business Perspective	The study was done on WFH for the Employees in the IT industry so research is done on sample data of 526 employees from IT as it shows that employees working in IT industry are increasing the productivity and are making best use of their resources in work from home. It was concluded that organizational and working environment plays a very significant

		role in the productivity.
Zhisheng Chen 2021	<i>Influence of Working From Home During the COVID-19 Crisis and HR Practitioner Organization Psychology</i> Research Review, (12)	The study says that pandemic has changed the life of many people so many people who are doing WFH are in stress so there should be good HR practices to be followed in the organizations as it improves work flexibility, psychological stress, etc. It was concluded that WFH has brought some relevant changes and has certain effects on workplace. It is benefitted for both employees and organizations.
K.D.V Prasad, Rajesh Vaidya and Ridhi Rani 2023	<i>Remote working and occupational stress: Effects on IT-enabled industry employees in Hyderabad Metro, India</i> Organizational Psychology Research Review, (14)	The study put focus on WFH and workplace stress on employees at their jobs with their effects on motivation, performance. There were sample collected from the employees of IT industry about 513 responses were collected. It was concluded that there are still many organizations who are creating challenges for the employees and are experiencing stress. It is essential for the employees to make their work accordingly so that employees do not take stress in doing work from home. It should be easier so that they can plan their days and can work efficiently as this will increase the output of organizations.
Amy Hackney, Marcus Yung, Kumara G., Somasundram, Behdin Nowrouzi Kia, Jodi Oakman, Amin Yazdani 2022	<i>Working in the digital economy: A systematic review of the impact of work from home arrangements on personal and organizational performance and productivity.</i> Research Article Research Review, 17(10)	The study says that work from home has laid down effects on physical and mental health of the employees and safety is also important for them. Organizations should use the resources in good way so that efficiency increases. The sample was taken from the employees working work from home. It was concluded that work from home is gaining popularity in many organizations and has positive effects too and work should be done by employees in efficient way so that stress level goes down as it increases productivity.
Jodi Oakman, Natasha Kinsman and Victoria Weale 2020	<i>A rapid review of mental and physical health effects of working from home: how do we optimise health</i> BMC Public Health Research Review, 20(20), 1-13	The study focuses on how work from home can help less stress and good health of the employees. Sample was collected from the employees who are doing work from home and has effects on physical health. There were different methods used for the study. It was concluded that there were several employees who are doing work from home are affected due to stress and their

		health is also affected. Its like there should be good relationship among employees regarding work. Management should also support the employees in their work so that they can work effectively.
Longqi Yang, David Holtz and Jaime Teevan 2022	<i>The effects of remote work on collaboration among workers</i> Nature Human Behaviour Research Review, 9(6), 43-54	The study focuses on effects of work from home over pandemic and other factors. This research focuses on work from home on large scale results found that there were some positive effects and negative effects. It concludes that work from home has positive effects and is very essential.
Lina Vyas and Nantapong Butakhieo 2020	<i>The impact of working from home during COVID-19 on work and life domains: An exploratory study on Hong Kong</i> Policy Design and Practice Research Review, 1(4), 59-76	The study says that there were large number of employees in pandemic who were not able to communicate regarding work through one another and this has affects to both employers and employees. Remote work has become a policy nowadays. It was concluded that remote work is not best for employees working in Hong Kong. There is least interest among employees in doing work from home.
Kdv Prasad, W Rajesh, Rajesh Vaidya and Rao Mruthyanjaya 2020	<i>Effect of occupational stress and remote working on psychological well-being of employees: An empirical analysis during COVID-19 pandemic concerning information technology industry in Hyderabad</i> Indian Journal of Commercial and Management Studies Research Review, 2(9)	The study says that many employees were forced to do work from home and were asked to opt it which result into many challenges among both employer and employee. It result into workplace stress on doing work from home which affects psychological well being in IT industry. It concludes that work from home is only option for the employees in pandemic and it will reduce stress level in them too. So employees and employer need to do work from home in pandemic in order to reduce stress.
Gayathri Ranjit and P Akhila 2021	<i>A study on Job Stress during work from home in the IT industry</i> Asian Journal of Sociological Research Research Review, 4(1), 282-291	The study focuses on reason for the stress of employees in the IT industry. It was found that stress has greater impact on the employees and it reduces productivity. It was found that if employees work in efficient way stress can be reduced and then only productivity increase. Employees need to use their resources effectively in order to reduce stress. As work from home has many advantages also. Effective measures have to be taken to reduce stress of employees and greater efficiency.
Dr. Jolly Sahini 2020	<i>Impact of COVID-19 on Employee Behavior: Stress and</i>	The study focuses on how the employer, employees and organizations have to

	<i>coping Mechanism During Work from Home Among Service Industry Employees</i> International Journal of Operation Management Research Review,1(1), 35-48	adapt the challenges in doing work from home. The impact of COVID-19 has affected physical health and occupational stress in employees and employer. Organizations have to build different strategies in order to cope up with stress. It was concluded that the pandemic has created stress in employees and many challenges in doing remote work. Employees need organization support and motivation to work effectively.
Sherrill W Hayes, Jennifer Priestly, Brian A Moore and Herman Roy 2021	<i>Perceived Stress, Work Related Burnout and Working from Home Before and During COVID-19: An Examination of Workers in the United States</i> Journal SAGE Research Review, 11(4), 1-12	The study focuses on work from home before and during the pandemic and stress level and burnout for employees. The sample of 256 data was collected from different employees who themselves were doing work from home. There were many challenges that were faced by the employees as communication, time management, coordination with technology. It has contributed high level of stress in employees. It concludes that as work from home increases employees will become pro in doing work from home.
Pratiksha Nair 2023	<i>Job Stress and Job Satisfaction among Employees Working from Home</i> Department of Sociology and Social Work Research Review, 1-14	The study tells us about the stress of job and satisfaction of job in doing work from home. This is a fact that now work from home has decreased level of stress and has increased job satisfaction. Many unemployed person are getting chance to do work from home. It concludes that there is a positive correlation between work from home and job satisfaction. So work from home has decreased stress.
Ritu Atheya and Dr. Renu Arora 2014	<i>Stress and its Brunt on Employees work life balance: A conceptual Study</i> International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research Review, 3(19), 57-62	The study focuses on stress on doing work from home and tells us that work life balance has become an issue at the organizations. As there is an increase in working hours and has to focus on many activities too. Work life balance is very important in every employee. It was concluded that stress in doing job in work from home is increasing and it is affecting the performance of the employees. There should be proper management in the organizations, as it will increase productivity in doing work.
Akanksha Jaiswal 2022	<i>Working from home during COVID-19 and its impact on Indian employees stress and</i>	The study focuses on work from home and it tells us that it has become a reality for many employees This study

	<i>creativity</i> Asian Business and Management Research Review, 1-25	tells us about American employees who are doing work from home. Organizations need to use right tools for better communication in work from home as timely video meetings, proper workforce.
Cristiano Cadagnone, Fabienne Abadie and Federico Biagi 2016	<i>The future of work in the Sharing Economy</i> JCR Science for Policy Report Research Review, 1-100	The study analyse the labour market and workers which do work from home. The researcher used different methods to analyse this. It was concluded that organization need to focus on contribution as size and growth in the future and types of labour market that needs to be used
Fiona Niebuhr, Prem Borle, Franziska Borner Zobel and Susanne Voelter Mahlknecht 2022	<i>Healthy and Happy Working from Home? Effects of Working from Home on Employee Health and Job Satisfaction</i> Int J Environ Res Public Health Research Review, 19(3)	The study tells that work from home has become a common place for every employee and it does affect health of the employees. It concludes that there is a rapid change in the worldwide. There are factors which affects health so there should be increase in job satisfaction of the employees and factors need to be implemented.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To Identify Key Challenges: *Objective:* Conduct a thorough literature review and empirical analysis to identify and categorize the key challenges faced by organizations in the service industry when implementing a work from home policy.

Productivity Levels: *Objective:* To evaluate how remote work influence productivity levels in IT professionals, considering both quantitative and qualitative output.

Employee Engagement: *Objective:* To understand employee engagement levels such as job satisfaction, motivation, emotional commitment to organization.

Work Life Balance: *Objective:* To examine work life balance including challenges and benefits.

To Assess Employee Productivity and Work life Balance: *Objective:* Measure the impact of remote work on employee productivity and job satisfaction using quantitative and qualitative methods, comparing performance metrics and job satisfaction surveys between in-office and remote working scenarios.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Objective:

Literature Review and Meta-Analysis: The objective of this research is to systematically review and analyze existing literature on the Impact of Remote Work on Employee Well-being in the Service Industry

DATA SOURCES:

Identification of Sources: Identify relevant academic journals, articles, conference papers, reports, and books related to remote work and its effects on employees. Utilize academic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and relevant organizational websites.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Define specific criteria for including or excluding sources, such as publication date range, relevance, and academic rigor.

DATA COLLECTION:

Literature Search: Conduct systematic searches using appropriate keywords and search strings to identify relevant literature.

Data Extraction: Extract pertinent information from selected sources, including study objectives, methods, findings, and key variables related to productivity, job satisfaction, wellbeing, self-discipline.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

There are direct variables such as job satisfaction, work life balance, significant positive work environment in IT professionals.

To know whether job satisfaction is not a significant moderator of above relationships as findings generally provide support for employees productivity in work from home.

To know whether work from home has helped employees in managing their time more effectively.

CONCLUSION

It has been noticed that different researchers have different perceptions in respect to work from home.

Proper work life balance is maintained in work from home by employees.

Employees when they are aware of their wellbeing have been taken care of by the organization, perform better and are more engaged which results into better productivity.

Organization has created an environment that is supportive and nurturing to employees.

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